

Distinct pathways to well-being: Exploring valued action and mood among stoics and non-stoics[☆]

Nicola V. Catts^a, Baljinder K. Sahdra^b, Joseph Ciarrochi^b, Madeleine I. Fraser^{a,c,*},
Cristóbal Hernández^d, Steven C. Hayes^e, Andrew T. Gloster^f

^a School of Behavioral Health Sciences, Australian Catholic University, Australia

^b Institute for Positive Psychology and Education, Australian Catholic University, Australia

^c Healthy Brain and Mind Research Centre, Australian Catholic University, Australia

^d Escuela de Psicología, Universidad Adolfo Ibáñez, Chile

^e University of Nevada, Reno and the Institute for Better Health, United States

^f University of Lucerne, Switzerland

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Valued action

Mood

Idiomatic

Experience sampling methodology

Clinical population

ABSTRACT

To examine the relationship between valued action and mood, this study analyzed Ecological Momentary Assessment data from a transdiagnostic in- and out-patient sample (EMA; $N = 134$; 62 female, 72 male; 62 inpatient, 72 outpatient; $M_{age} = 36.6$ years, $SD = 11.6$). Individual time series models were constructed to capture each participant's unique relationship between valued action and mood. The models were then meta-analyzed, revealing substantial variability, with two subgroups; Stoics ($n = 64$) and Non-Stoics ($n = 70$). The Stoics subgroup showed null or negative links between valued action and mood, replicating past findings from a nonclinical sample. The Non-Stoic group engaged significantly more in valued actions characterized by enjoyment and relaxation. Subsequent multilevel VAR networks were created to examine differences between Stoics and Non-Stoics. Within-person analyses indicated that, unlike Non-Stoics, Stoics showed no significant association between valued action and mood in contemporaneous networks. Temporal networks revealed that, for Non-Stoics, mood positively influenced future engagement in valued action. These findings challenge assumptions of a universally positive relationship between valued action and mood, suggesting divergent paths to well-being based on individual differences in mood-action dynamics.

1. Different paths to well-being: the link between valued action and mood amongst stoics and non-stoics

Psychologists are, largely, in the business of alleviating human suffering. However, suffering, at least in Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT), is seen as part of the human condition (Hayes, Stroschal, & Wilson, 2012). How do we then alleviate human suffering if it is inherent to the experience of being human, and likely the result of a constellation of factors that are unique to these individuals?

According to ACT, human suffering increases in intensity or is

prolonged when we struggle with, try to suppress, and avoid suffering (Hayes, Stroschal, & Wilson, 2012). Additionally, these attempts to avoid suffering change our behaviours, often drawing us away from living our life in line with our values. The solution, at least as proposed in ACT, is to “drop the struggle” (Harris, 2019, p. 101) and accept suffering in our lives while still committing to actions that are in line with our values (Hayes, Stroschal, & Wilson, 2012; Harris, 2019). Despite this, many people, including clinicians, believe that valued action can only occur in the absence of suffering or after suffering has been alleviated (c.f. Gloster et al., 2017). Additionally, much of the research on which we

[☆] This study involved secondary data analysis from a previously published study (Gloster et al., 2023). This study was registered with Open Science Framework (osf.io/u93sf). Data will be made available upon reasonable request once accepted for publication. Generative artificial intelligence tools were not used in the writing or editing of this manuscript. Given their roles at JCBSA/Prof. Baljinder K. Sahdra (Editor-in-Chief) and Dr. Cristobal Hernandez (Editorial Board Member) had no involvement in the peer-review of this article and no access to information regarding its peer-review. We have no other conflicts of interest to disclose.

* Corresponding author, School of Behavioural Health Sciences, Australian Catholic University, 25a Barker Road, Strathfield campus, Sydney, NSW, 2135, Australia.

E-mail address: madeleine.fraser@acu.edu.au (M.I. Fraser).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcbs.2025.100898>

Received 12 February 2025; Received in revised form 10 April 2025; Accepted 22 April 2025

Available online 23 April 2025

2212-1447/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Inc. on behalf of Association for Contextual Behavioral Science. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

base this assumption assumes psychological homogeneity, or that these processes affect every individual within the group in the same way. In this study we sought to examine the relationship between valued action and hedonic well-being using a novel Idionomic approach.

In contrast, nomothetic methods are based on several assumptions, one of which is the assumption of psychological homogeneity, that is, a psychological process will have the same effect on every individual within that group. This often assumes that deviations from the normative pattern are due to error or unexplainable deviations from the “true” signal (Ciarrochi et al., 2024b; Sahdra et al., 2024). An emerging body of evidence is starting to call into question this assumption of psychological homogeneity (Ciarrochi, et al., 2024a, 2024b; Sahdra et al., 2024).

1.1. The problem of ergodicity and the idionomic solution

In clinical practice, clinicians often apply research based on group averages (nomothetic findings), to individual clients based on clinical judgment of their applicability. However, Molenaar (2004) showed that applying insights from a collection of people to particular people cannot be reliably done unless these variables or combination of variables are ergodic. Ergodic processes are those for which there are no systematic trends over time and inter-individual variation is the same as intra-individual variation (Molenaar, 2004, 2013; Molenaar & Campbell, 2009).

Fisher et al. (2018) suggest that previously unexamined violations of ergodicity could have far-reaching implications for psychological science as we know it. Although it may be premature and impractical to consider all nomothetic findings as only applicable to similar samples from known populations and not particular people, it does mean that researchers need to demonstrate consistency between group-level findings and individual findings before results can be generalised across these levels (Fisher et al., 2018). Emerging idionomic research methods offer a solution to address these potentially paradigm-shifting concerns (Hayes et al., 2022). Idionomic research is not a statistical method per se, but a newly established attitude toward research that examines intraindividual (idiographic) psychological processes, and then expands these to interindividual (nomothetic) findings if and only if they illuminate or improve the fit of the intraindividual findings (Ciarrochi et al., 2024a, 2024b; Hayes et al., 2022; Sahdra et al., 2023, 2024). These idiographic findings may then be supportive of previous nomothetic findings, or may identify particular subgroups of individuals who vary from these findings, or may show that no nomothetic aggregation is appropriate (Fisher et al., 2018; Gloster et al., 2023).

Gloster et al. (2023) examined an idionomic approach to analysis in a transdiagnostic sample of previously non-treatment-responsive inpatients. These researchers found that nomothetic analyses hid highly variable individual trajectories, including deteriorating outcomes, and they were able to identify subgroups of participants who had meaningful different relationships between trajectories and outcomes. These insights would have been lost if only traditional nomothetic methodologies were employed. These preliminary findings have important implications. If nomothetic analyses are not representative of many individuals within the group, then the ability to apply these findings reliably to individuals is called into question. Evidence-based practice in psychology involves combining clinical expertise and the best available research in the context of the client characteristics, culture, and preferences (APA, 2005) This is not to suggest that all our best available nomothetic research is therefore invalid, rather that we now have a pathway forward to develop and apply research methods that may better support clinical expertise as it applies to the individual (Hayes et al., 2022). Additionally, an idionomic analytic approach still allows for and may even improve the ability to make nomothetic generalisations (e.g., Sahdra et al., 2024).

1.2. The present study

Sahdra et al. (2024) used a sample of 425 college students' Ecological Momentary Analysis (EMA) data to determine whether idionomic methods added insight to the relationship between valued action and affect. They compared idionomic analyses to the dominant nomothetic statistical modeling technique for EMA studies, multilevel models (MLM). They found in the idionomic analyses that the relationship between the process and outcome was the opposite to that found in the nomothetic effect for some individuals. Specifically, they found two meaningfully different subgroups named Stoics and Non-Stoics. Stoics, in Sahdra et al. (2024), were defined as those for whom the relationship between valued action and joyfulness was negative and the relationship between valued action and sadness was positive. This was the opposite of what was expected based on previous nomothetic research and the nomothetic (MLM) analysis results using the same data. Non-Stoics, conversely, were defined as those for whom the relationship between valued action and joyfulness and sadness was in the expected direction. Additionally, when examining the network analysis, valued action was more likely in stressful situations but this valued action was neither linked to joy nor sadness in the short term in the Stoic group. These findings demonstrated that meaningful differences between the groups were hidden when the MLM results were examined. Like Gloster et al. (2023), these results support the assertion that important clinical insights may be lost when using purely nomothetic methods, whereas idionomic methods allow for the preservation of individual insights and often, the identification of meaningful subgroups of individuals. Additionally, these findings suggest that although previous nomothetic findings may hold for many clients, there is likely a subset for whom increasing engagement in valued action may not increase hedonic well-being.

There are a few notable limitations in Sahdra et al.'s (2024) study. Firstly, participants were a college student sample, which limits the applicability of findings to clinical populations. Secondly, although they identified two subgroups, there was no information about why Stoics did not experience greater hedonic well-being from valued action. Therefore, the present study aims to extend upon the findings of Sahdra et al. (2024) in a transdiagnostic in- and out-patient psychiatric sample, and add additional measures to better characterize these sub-groups. Our research questions are:

(R1) Can the findings of Sahdra et al. (2024) be reproduced in a transdiagnostic in- and out-patient sample? Specifically, we ask if there is significant heterogeneity in individual effects between mood and valued action, and if so, whether we can identify meaningful subgroups, including a group (Stoics) for whom the relationship between mood and valued action substantially deviates from the norm?

Building upon the first research question, we ask: What are the between-, within-person, and temporal relationships between mood, valued action, and reaction to valued activity for those who substantially deviate from the norm (Stoics) as compared to the rest of the sample (R2)? Our final question asks what kind of activities the Stoics engage in that may differ from those the non-Stoics engage in (R3)?

2. Method

2.1. Participants

We conducted a secondary analysis of an existing de-identified data set. The original study, “Choose Change” (Gloster et al., 2023; Villanueva et al., 2019; ISRCTN: ISRCTN11209732), was approved by the Ethics Committee of Northwestern and Central Switzerland (Ethikkommission Nordwest – und Zentralschweiz, EKNZ; Project 165/13). Approval for secondary data analysis was granted by the Australian Catholic University Human Research Ethics Committee (Approval number: 2024-3570X). Secondary data analysis plan for the current study was pre-registered (osf.io/u93sf). The current study analyzed data

from 134 participants (62 female, 72 male, 62 inpatient, 72 outpatient, $M_{age} = 36.6$ years, $SD = 11.6$). The original data was collected in two psychology clinics in Switzerland which specialised in Acceptance and Commitment Therapy. As ACT is conceptualized as a transdiagnostic therapy (Dindo et al., 2017), inclusion and exclusion criteria were kept to a minimum. Inclusion criteria included: Over the age of 18, sufficient German language skills, ability to attend the sessions, previous treatment of greater than or equal to 20 sessions of evidence-based treatment and/or minimum drug treatment as recommended by international guidelines, and ability to consent. Exclusion criteria included acute suicidal intent, acute substance dependency requiring detoxification, active mania, previous experience with ACT, and the inability to read or complete the assessment.

2.2. Procedure

At baseline, the research team provided each participant with a smartphone and instructions on how to use it for collecting Ecological Momentary Assessment (EMA) data. The participants were signaled approximately every 3 h (six times a day) for seven days to complete the EMA questionnaire. This procedure was repeated at baseline, post, and follow-up, but the data of interest to this study is baseline data only, thus although some of the participants may have previously received treatment, they were not exposed to this intervention administered as part of the original study (Villanueva et al., 2019) at the time of data collection. For an illustration of study design in the original study, please see Fig. 1 in Villanueva et al. (2019).

2.3. Measures

All EMA items are presented in Table 1. The intraclass correlation coefficient - 1 or ICC (1) was examined as an estimate of between-person variance, and the ICC (2) was examined as an estimate of the reliability of EMA items. The ICC (1) ranged from 0.17 to 0.43, representing relatively low between-person variance and, conversely, relatively high within-person variance. The novel single-item measures in the current study have not been previously validated, however, the ICC (2) for all items ranged from 0.84 to 0.96 suggesting good to excellent reliability for all EMA items (Koo & Li, 2016).

2.3.1. Valued action

Valued action items began with the prompt “Please think about your

Table 1
Ecological momentary assessment items and their intraclass correlation coefficients.

Construct – construct name referred to in text	EMA Item	ICC (1) [95 % CI]	ICC (2) [95 % CI]
1. Valued action – In Line	Please think about your time since the last prompt ... Is it in line with the way you want to live your life?	0.30 [0.25, 0.36]	0.92 [0.95,0.97]
2. Valued action – Want to Spend	Please think about your time since the last prompt ... Did you actually want to spend your time this way?	0.17 [0.13,0.21]	0.84 [0.80, 0.88]
3. Current Mood – Mood	How would you rate your current mood?	0.43 [0.36, 0.49]	0.96 [0.95, 0.97]
4. Reaction to valued activity - Overwhelming	Please think about your time since the last prompt ... Did it overwhelm you?	0.27 [0.22, 0.32]	0.91 [0.88, 0.93]
5. Reaction to valued activity - Positive	Please think about your time since the last prompt ... Did you find it positive?	0.22 [0.17,0.27]	0.88 [0.84, 0.90]

time since the last prompt ...” and assessed whether participants took actions in the last 3 h that were “in line with the way you want to live your life” (In Line) and whether they “actually want to spend your time this way?” (Want to Spend). Valued action items were measured on a slider from 0 (not at all) to 100 (very much). In the current study, In Line was found to have excellent reliability, ICC (2) = 0.92 [0.95,0.97] and Want to Spend was found to have good reliability, ICC (2) = 0.84 [0.80, 0.88] (Koo & Li, 2016).

2.3.2. Reaction to valued activity

Reaction to valued activity items began with the same prompt “Please think about your time since the last prompt” and assessed whether these activities “overwhelmed you?” (Overwhelm) and did they “find it positive?” (Positive). Reaction to valued activity items were measured on a slider from 0 (not at all) to 100 (very much). In the current study, Overwhelm was found to have excellent reliability, ICC (2) = 0.91 [0.88, 0.93], and Positive was found to have good reliability, ICC (2) = 0.88 [0.84, 0.90].

2.3.3. Current mood

Participants were also asked to indicate on a 6-point Likert scale from 0 (very bad) to 5 (very good) “How would you rate your current mood?” (Mood). In the current study, Mood was found to have excellent reliability, ICC (2) = 0.96 [0.95, 0.97].

2.3.4. Values domains

Participants were then asked to assign their response to the current mood question to one of 12 areas based on their behaviour at the time of data collection: Work/school (average frequency of endorsement = 14.40 %), Being on the way from A to B (4.40 %), Media/TV/Internet (5.00 %), Contact with family/conversation (6.49 %), Contact with other people/conversation (15.06 %), Being on my own/bored (2.00 %), Shopping/household (7.26 %), Leisure (excluding physical activities) (3.46 %), Physical Activity (5.97 %), Eat/Drink (7.09 %), Enjoy/Relax (17.14 %), or Other (11.74 %).

2.4. Data analyses

Analyses were conducted in R version 4.3.3 (R Core Team, 2024). The average number of observations per participant was 31.34, with a range of 11–42. Mean missing data of the EMA items was 16.5 % for In Line, Want to Spend, Overwhelming, and Positive. Mean missing data of EMA item Mood was 0 %. Missing data were not imputed, and the cut-off for inclusion in the analysis was 10 observations. All available data was used to make individual level estimates.

2.4.1. Preliminary analyses

Analyses began with descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis) and correlations between mean between-person (average across all time points) scores on all EMA variables (See Table 2). As within-person variability is of interest to the present study, we then ran within-person (averaged across measurements) correlations of all EMA variables. (See Table 3). All data were person-centered prior to analysis. Our idiographic approach involved estimating models separately for each individual, ensuring that parameter estimates reflected within-person patterns rather than being influenced by between-person differences. As a result, the global mean did not affect any individual’s estimates, preserving the idiographic integrity of the analysis.

2.4.2. Idiographic modeling using the i-ARIMAX algorithm

To estimate the strength of the relationship between In Line and Mood, we employed AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average with an exogenous variable (ARIMAX) models for each individual (the ‘i’ in i-ARIMAX). Although it is possible to estimate the strength of these relationships using correlations or regression analyses, our data was likely to violate the assumptions of these analyses. Therefore, as in Sahdra

et al. (2024) and Ciarrochi et al. (2024), we elected to use i-ARIMAX modeling, an extension of ARIMA modeling, which accounts for violations of stationarity and independence.

Although we did not explicitly include time as a covariate, we controlled for temporal structure using ARIMA modeling, which incorporates p (autoregressive), d (differencing), and q (moving average) components. These parameters account for time-dependent patterns in the data. In particular, the d parameter addresses trends by differencing the time series—removing nonstationary components such as gradual increases or decreases over time. This process effectively detrends the data, helping to isolate fluctuations due to meaningful relationships rather than time-based drift. Thus, even without directly modeling time as a predictor, the ARIMA framework accounts for temporal dynamics in a robust and data-driven way. Additionally, i-ARIMAX allows for an exogenous variable (X) that only predicts the outcome. In the current study the exogenous variable was In Line and the outcome was Mood. The i-ARIMAX procedure provided an estimate of the effect size and standard error.

2.4.3. Examining heterogeneity: Random-Effects Meta-Analysis (RE-MA)

To examine heterogeneity, we meta-analyzed the resulting i-ARIMAX relationships using Random-Effects Meta-Analysis (RE-MA). We used each individual model as a proxy for a study effect and an estimate of error to determine the pooled effect and the heterogeneity of effects. We examined heterogeneity of effects through Cochran’s Q test of heterogeneity (used to test the statistical significance of heterogeneity) and I² (percentage of total variability across studies due to non-random heterogeneity – systematic differences between people – rather than due to chance). There are no definitive cut-offs for the interpretation of I². However, in meta-analytic research if I² exceeds 50 %, the pooled effect may be misleading (Higgins et al., 2022). Thus, we looked for meaningful subgroups if there was substantial non-random heterogeneity, as indicated by an I² greater than 50 %.

2.4.4. Subgroup-level aggregation

We chose to aggregate subgroups based on whether the relationship between In Line and Mood was significantly positive (i.e. the expected nomothetic effect, Non-Stoics), or whether there was a null or negative relationship (i.e. no effect or the opposite of the expected nomothetic effect; Stoics). Sahdra et al. (2024) warned against the reification of the Stoic vs. Non-Stoic categories. Therefore, rather than treating Stoic and Non-Stoic as fixed categories, we conceptualized these as part of a continuum based on the relationship between valued action and mood. Individuals closer to the "Stoic" end showed weaker or reversed associations between valued action and mood, while those closer to the "Non-Stoic" end showed the expected associations.

2.4.5. Modeling relationships within subgroups: multilevel vector autoregression modeling (Multilevel-VAR)

Using a Multilevel-VAR, we aimed to examine the between-person, within-person contemporaneous, and temporal networks for the two groups. Specifically, our goal was to compare the interrelations of all EMA items for the Stoics compared to the rest of the sample (Non-Stoics). As Multilevel-VAR models estimate every possible link between every node (variable), the average number of observations were 31.34.

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics and raw correlations for the between-person (average across time) relationships for all EMA Variables.

EMA Variable	M	SD	Skew	Kurtosis	1	2	3	4	5
1. In Line	67.6	24.8	-0.890	0.282	1				
2. Want to Spend	70.0	24.7	-1.05	0.535	0.85	1			
3. Mood	3.12	1.04	-0.478	0.103	0.62	0.59	1		
4. Overwhelming	30.1	26.2	0.755	-0.548	-0.42	-0.44	-0.62	1	
5. Positive	72.2	21.9	-1.17	1.31	0.74	0.79	0.72	-0.58	1

Note. All correlations are significant at the p < 0.001 level. See the Method section for a full description of each item.

Table 3

Raw correlations for the between-person (average across measurements) relationships for all EMA variables.

EMA Variable	1	2	3	5	5
1. In Line	1				
2. Want to Spend	0.74	1			
3. Mood	0.37	0.35	1		
4. Overwhelming	-0.29	-0.37	-0.42	1	
5. Positive	0.61	0.68	0.45	-0.45	1

Note. All correlations are significant at p < 0.001 level. See the Method section for a full description of each item.

Given that the relationships of interest were those between valued action and hedonic well-being, we chose to include only five variables in the multilevel-VAR networks: In Line, Want to Spend, Mood, Overwhelm, and Positive.

Analysis of Variance tests were used to determine whether the Stoics and Non-Stoics differ in terms of mean (average across measurement occasions) levels of all EMA items. Additionally, chi-squared tests of independence were performed to examine any difference of group (Stoic vs. Non-Stoic) based on age, gender, and clinic type (i.e. inpatient vs. Outpatient).

2.4.6. Examining group differences

Finally, using a one-way ANOVA, we examined the differences of groups (Stoic vs. Non-Stoic) based on values domains.

3. Results

3.1. Descriptive statistics and raw between- and within-person correlations

Table 2 reports the descriptive statistics and raw between-person (averaged across time) correlations for all EMA variables. There was some negative skew for some EMA variables but this is common for mental health variables (Gonzalez-Blanks et al., 2020). All correlations were significant at the p < 0.001 level.

Between-person analysis. In Line was positively correlated with a Positive reaction to the valued activity (Positive), the way the participant wanted to spend their time (Want to Spend), and Mood. In Line was also negatively correlated with an overwhelming reaction to the valued activity (Overwhelm). This suggests that individuals with higher-than-average alignment with their values also tended to experience more positive reactions, engage in activities they preferred, and report better mood, while feeling less overwhelmed.

Within-person analysis. Table 3 presents the raw within-person correlations (averaged across measurements) of the Ecological Momentary Assessment (EMA) items, all significant at the p < 0.001 level. Within individuals, in moments when they acted more in line with their values, they experienced more positive reactions, engaged in activities they preferred, and reported better mood, while feeling less overwhelmed.

Fig. 1. Distribution of i-ARIMAX estimates by effect size band.

3.2. I-ARIMAX models and multivariate Random-Effects Meta-Analysis

Although the between- and within-person correlations demonstrated similar relationships, they were based on averages and ignored the individual variability of interest to this study. Specifically, to answer research question 1, we were interested in examining the heterogeneity of the individual relationships between In Line and Mood.

We conducted individual i-ARIMAX analyses of the In Line and Mood pairing for each participant. Each i-ARIMAX model provided an estimate of the strength of the relationship between In Line and Mood (effect size), and a standard error. Fig. 1 shows the frequency of individuals within each effect size band. The effect sizes ranged from -0.5 to 0.9, with most values falling between -0.2 and 0.9.

To investigate the heterogeneity of effects, we ran RE-MA models. The pooled effect for mood was positive ($\beta = 0.321$; $SE = 0.023$) with a 95 % confidence interval ranging from 0.275 to 0.367. The effect was significant ($p < 0.001$). However, there was substantial non-random heterogeneity within the model ($I^2 = 72.72\%$), suggesting that the pooled effect, despite having a relatively narrow confidence interval, should be interpreted with caution as it may fail to reflect individual estimates and further investigation of meaningful subgroups is

warranted (Iannidis et al., 2007). Additionally, the Cochran’s Q test (Huedo-Medina et al., 2006), indicated that the degree of heterogeneity was significant: Cochran’s $Q(133) = 718.62, p < 0.0001$.

To explore the heterogeneity identified in the meta-analysis, Fig. 2 shows a forest plot of the within-person relationship between In Line and Mood for each individual. The green lines represent those individuals for whom the relationship between In Line and Mood was positive, the red lines represent those for whom the relationship was negative, and the black lines represent those for whom there was no significant relationship. Although there was a substantial group who appeared to be consistent with expectations based on the raw correlations and previous nomothetic findings (i.e., the green lines; Gregoire et al., 2021; Gloster et al., 2017; Tunc et al., 2023; Villate et al., 2016), there was also a substantial number for whom either the relationship was either null (the black lines) or the opposite of the raw correlations and the previous nomothetic effects seen in the literature and in this study (means that fall below the mean confidence interval and are relatively close to zero).

3.3. Subgroup-level aggregation

We separated those for whom the relationship between In Line and Mood was either null or negative (who we will call the Stoics) from those for whom the relationship between In Line and Mood was positive (who we will call the Non-Stoics). Sahdra et al. (2024) defined their Stoic group as those for whom the relationship between valued action and affect was the opposite of the expected nomothetic effect, but our results yielded only one such person, which would have left us with insufficient power to perform network analysis on people who have a strong link between mood and values and those who have a weaker link. We therefore chose to classify Stoics as those who did not have a reliable positive link between acting in line with values and mood.

3.4. Within-person contemporaneous, between-person, and temporal networks of variables: Multilevel-VAR

To answer research question 2, we conducted separate multilevel-VAR models for the Stoics and the Non-Stoics, to compare the relationships between the two-valued action items (In Line and Want to

Fig. 2. Forest Plot of the within-person relationships between In Line and Mood.

Note. Green lines represent positive relationships, black lines represent no relationship, and red lines represent negative relationships. Blue lines are the 95 % confidence interval of the overall mean. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Spend), Mood, and reaction to valued activity items (Positive and Overwhelm). Due to power issues with some participants only providing small amounts of EMA data, we limited the number of variables within the network to those focused on values and mood. We examined the within-person contemporaneous, between-person, and temporal networks in the Stoic and Non-Stoic groups.

Fig. 3 shows the within-person contemporaneous networks for the Stoics (n = 64) and Non-Stoics (n = 70). Red coloured lines represent negative relationships and green coloured lines represent positive relationships, with the thickness of the lines representing the strength of each relationship. The Stoics (Fig. 3, left panel) had no relationship between In Line and Mood in their network, whereas the Non-Stoics (Fig. 3, right panel) had a positive relationship. Interestingly, the Stoics appeared to have a positive relationship between In Line and Overwhelm and no relationship between Want to Spend and Overwhelm, whereas the Non-Stoics had no relationship between In Line and Overwhelm and a negative relationship between Want to Spend and Overwhelm. This suggested that when stoics acted in line with their values, they were more likely to feel overwhelmed. All other relationships between the groups were in the same direction.

Fig. 4 shows the between-person networks for the Stoics and Non-Stoics. The between-person network for the Stoics (Fig. 4, left panel) differed from the within-person network in that there was a positive relationship between In Line and Mood and the relationship between In Line and Overwhelm disappeared. All other relationships in the between-person Stoics network corresponded with the raw correlations. Interestingly for the Non-Stoics (Fig. 4, right panel) the between-person network shows no relationship between Positive and Overwhelm and a negative relationship between Mood and Want to Spend.

Fig. 5 shows the temporal networks for the Stoics and Non-Stoics with a lag of 1. For this study, we used a T-1 lag. For the Non-Stoic group, Mood precedes the extent that action is in line with values, whereas for the Stoic group, there is no such relationship.

Finally, we explored group differences in demographics and other variables. Pearson’s Chi-Squared test with Yates continuity correction (due to smaller sample sizes) showed that Stoics and Non-Stoics did not significantly differ based on gender ($\chi^2(1, N = 134) = 0.002, p = 0.969$) or clinic type (i.e. Inpatient or Outpatient) ($\chi^2(1, n = 134) = 2.034, p = 0.1540$). Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test (due to smaller sample sizes and non-normal distributions) showed that Stoics and Non-Stoics did not

significantly differ in age ($\chi^2(1, N = 134) = 0.207, p = 0.649$). A one-way ANOVA showed that Stoics vs. Non-Stoics did not significantly differ in mean levels of Positive [$F(1,132) = 0.034, p = 0.854$], Overwhelm [$F(1,132) = 0.563, p = 0.455$], Want to Spend [$F(1,132) = 0.058, p = 0.81$], In Line [$F(1,132) = 0, p = 0.99$], or Mood [$F(1,132) = 0.121, p = 0.729$].

3.5. Differences between Stoic and Non-Stoic domains of valued action

To consider how the Stoic and Non-Stoic groups may differ and to answer research question 3, we examined whether the groups differed in their engagement in specific domains of valued activity. Although these results should be interpreted with caution due to the high number of analyses which may increase the familywise error rate, there was a significant effect of group on valued domain Enjoy/Relax [$F(1,132) = 4.23, p = 0.042$]. The Non-Stoic group engaged in significantly more valued action that they characterised as time spent Enjoying/Relaxing ($M = 5.14, SD = 4.01$), than the Stoic group ($M = 3.87, SD = 3.12$). All other group differences were non-significant (See Table A1 in Appendix for full results).

4. Discussion

In this study, we aimed to extend upon the findings of Sahdra et al. (2024) in a transdiagnostic in- and out-patient sample by examining individual relationships between valued action and mood and identifying factors influencing these relationships. Our findings support Sahdra et al. (2024), showing that a significant subgroup of participants displayed a relationship between valued action and mood that diverged from previous nomothetic findings (Gregoire et al., 2021; Tunc et al., 2023; Villate et al., 2016). Traditional nomothetic analyses (correlations and pooled effects) masked considerable heterogeneity in these relationships. Furthermore, we identified meaningful differences between groups, offering insights that could inform both clinical and research practices.

Despite significant heterogeneity in the relationship between valued action and mood at the individual level, we identified meaningful and theoretically coherent subgroups at a nomothetic level. Specifically, we found a continuum ranging from Stoicism—where valued action is not linked to positive affective states—to Non-Stoicism—where valued

Fig. 3. Within-Person Contemporaneous Multilevel-VAR Networks

Note. Green lines represent positive relationships, red lines represent negative relationships, the thickness of each line represents the strengths of the relationships. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 4. Between-Person Multilevel-VAR Networks
 Note. Green lines represent positive relationships, red lines represent negative relationships, the thickness of each line represents the strengths of the relationships. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 5. Temporal Multilevel-VAR Networks
 Note. Green lines represent positive relationships, red lines represent negative relationships, the thickness of each line represents the strengths of the relationships. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

action is associated with improved mood. Unlike [Sahdra et al. \(2024\)](#), who identified 17 participants with a negative relationship between valued action and affect in a student sample, we found only one such case. Nevertheless, the broader Stoic to Non-Stoic continuum held.

The groups also showed distinct patterns among EMA variables. Unlike the Non-Stoics, the Stoics appeared to have no relationship between valued action and mood, as expected from the results of the i-ARIMAX modeling, which corresponded with the findings of [Sahdra et al., 2024](#). The Stoics were more likely to engage in valued action that was experienced as overwhelming despite no concurrent positive effects on mood. Additionally, when examining the temporal networks, amongst Non-Stoics, better mood preceded valued action in the short-term. Although in ACT, engagement in valued action is considered a desired clinical outcome, irrespective of the impact on mood in the

short-term, the current research suggests that for some client's interventions that target mood directly may be a necessary precursor to valued action. Again, this signifies the need for caution when relying on nomothetic findings in clinical practice.

To enhance the clinical utility of the current study, we wanted to know what differentiates these groups. We found no significant differences between the Stoics and Non-Stoics based on average valued activity, mood, or the experience of those valued activities as either positive or overwhelming. However, valued action was not mood-dependent for the Stoics, unlike the Non-Stoics, and was often overwhelming, which may be because the Non-Stoics engaged in more enjoyable and relaxing activities than the Stoics. Holding different values may differentiate these groups, and at least in the short-term, indicates that valued action for Stoics did not necessarily promote a

better mood. However, in the long term, both groups experienced equally positive moods.

4.1. Implications for research and clinical practice

Clinically, these results suggest that if the desired outcome is to improve mood, there may be a substantial group of clients for whom increasing engagement in valued action may have no effect (a benign outcome). For some, however, there may be worsening mood as a result (which may be a potentially harmful outcome). Although an increase in valued action is considered a desired outcome (Hayes et al., 2011), and a short-term dip in mood is not necessarily a cause for major concern if the long-term implications are a decrease in suffering overall, it does call into question the previous assumption that the pathway between valued action and mood/well-being/affect is necessarily always a positive one.

Additionally, valued action in this context was linked for some participants to feeling overwhelmed. This is not a desired clinical outcome even in the short-term, because a sense of feeling overwhelmed may be linked to a high arousal and perseveration on previously learned unhelpful behaviours (Ciria et al., 2021). These results call for caution when applying any intervention based on group-level findings to the individual client.

The larger implication of these findings is for the current normative research paradigm in psychology. We are already grappling with a replication crisis (Munafò et al., 2017), that has seen previous nomothetic findings called into question. This current program of research is beginning to show that perhaps it is not just that nomothetic findings are unreliable across studies, but the hegemony of nomothetic research methods itself may be inhibiting progress (Ciarrochi et al., 2024; Hayes et al., 2022; Sahdra et al., 2024).

4.2. Limitations and future directions

The present study utilised an existing dataset that included a diverse group of participants. Some participants had completed a previous psychological treatment, and others had not. Although not specifically measured nor accounted for in this study, future research could control for such experiences as a history of treatment resistance may be a confounding variable, creating a meaningful subgroup of participants with similar patterns in their mood and experience of valued action.

Common to many EMA studies, we utilised single-item measures (Gertler & Tate, 2020; Verster et al., 2021). However, despite being highly reliable, the exact wording of these measures were not previously validated. Approaching validity of single-item measures in an idiomonic context is complex given the issues highlighted previously in nomothetic analyses, however, Song et al. (2023) suggest that in EMAs, single-item measures may represent sound validity due to the inherent nature of the design. That is, each participant is able to form an internally consistent interpretation of the items upon repeated responding, particularly if the constructs being measured have sufficiently narrow meaning (Mouatt et al., 2023; Song et al., 2023; van Rijsbergen et al., 2013; Verster et al., 2021). Although these items may appear face valid, and similar items have been shown to be valid (Gertler & Tate, 2020; Verster et al., 2021), future research is needed to establish criterion validity of these single-item measures (Allen et al., 2022).

Due to the nature of the available data and the need for large within-person observations to support our statistical analyses, we were unable to directly replicate the proportions of participants classified as “Stoic” or “Non-Stoic” to include all participants showing a null or negative relationship between valued action and mood. We acknowledge that this approach inflated the proportion of individuals labelled “Stoic”. However, our primary goal was not to estimate the prevalence of stoics in the population—as we view this binary distinction as somewhat arbitrary—but to replicate and extend the key finding that the value–feeling relationship varies substantially across individuals and is not well captured by group averages. We interpret this variation as a continuum

of stoicism, and the groupings we use are intended to help describe and explore this continuum, not to suggest discrete types. If we examine the results based on effect size, we find that 49 participants (36.57 %) had a strong positive effect of the relationship between valued action and mood (greater than 0.5; in line with nomothetic findings), but 44 participants (32.84 %) had a small positive to negative effect of the relationship between valued action and mood (less than 0.2). Although our research lends support to the findings of Sahdra et al. (2024), future research may aim to directly replicate the methods of Sahdra et al. (2024) with a larger sample to examine these effects more closely.

Although our findings support Sahdra et al. (2024) and suggest the effect may extend beyond a single context or client group, we cannot assume it remains stable beyond seven days or generalizes beyond the populations studied. Future research should examine this effect over longer time periods, across diverse demographics, and explore how interventions or prior treatment non-response may influence the relationship between valued action and mood—especially if the effect continues to replicate.

Although we presented the temporal networks for each group above, these should be interpreted cautiously. Utilising a T-1 lag showed that for the Non-Stoics, a better mood preceded valued action, and a longer EMA time series may allow for the examination of different lags, different statistical techniques, and additional contextual variables. We were prevented from examining longer temporal lags in the present study due to an insufficient number of within-person observations to provide adequate power. Our current research adds some additional insight into what processes may be differentiating those from the norm, specifically, that Non-Stoics appeared to engage in more valued activity that they viewed as enjoyable and relaxing - and by extension may therefore be more reinforcing. Additional qualitative research would be beneficial, particularly for those who deviate substantially from the “norm”.

5. Conclusion

A program of research is beginning to show that clinical psychology findings from nomothetic or group-level research cannot always be reliably applied to the individual. We have shown here that, for specific individual clients, in certain contexts, and for certain types of valued activity, the relationship between that activity and better mood is less clear than previously assumed. If we had relied solely on group-level findings, we would continue to assume that what is good for the gander (the group) is good for the goose (the individual client). We must continue to utilise idiomonic methods to increase our evidence base for interventions and enrich our clinical judgment, particularly for clients who do not fit the norm.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Nicola V. Catts: Writing – original draft. **Baljinder K. Sahdra:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Joseph Ciarrochi:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Madeleine I. Fraser:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Cristóbal Hernández:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Steven C. Hayes:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Andrew T. Gloster:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Investigation, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Please note, A/Prof Baljinder Sahdra and A/Prof Cristobal Hernandez are on the editorial board of JCBS and are co-authors on the submitted

paper. We have also acknowledged this in our cover letter and title page. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known

competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix

Table A1
ANOVA of Group by Value Domain

Value Domain	Stoic		Non-Stoic		F (1,132)	P value
	M	SD	M	SD		
Enjoy/Relax	3.87	3.12	5.14	4.01	4.23*	0.042
Contact with family/conversation	1.84	2.63	1.53	1.72	0.65	0.423
Leisure (excl. physical activity)	1.06	2.27	0.73	1.5	0.92	0.339

Note. * $p < 0.05$.

References

- Allen, M. S., Iliescu, D., & Greiff, S. (2022). Single item measures in psychological science: A call to action. *European Journal of Psychological Assessment: Official Organ of the European Association of Psychological Assessment*, 38(1), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1015-5759/a000699>
- Ciarrochi, J., Sahdra, B., Fraser, M. I., Hayes, S. C., Yap, K., & Gloster, A. T. (2024). The compassion connection: Experience sampling insights into romantic attraction. *Journal of Contextual Behavioral Science*, 32, Article 100749. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcbs.2024.100749>
- Ciarrochi, J., Sahdra, B., Hayes, S. C., Hofmann, S. G., Sanford, B., Stanton, C., et al. (2024b). A personalised approach to identifying important determinants of well-being. *Cognitive therapy and research*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10608-024-10486-w>
- Ciria, L. F., Suárez-Pinilla, M., Williams, A. G., Jagannathan, S. R., Sanabria, D., & Bekinschtein, T. A. (2021). Different underlying mechanisms for high and low arousal in probabilistic learning in humans. *Cortex; a Journal Devoted to the Study of the Nervous System and Behavior*, 143, 180–194. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cortex.2021.07.002>
- Dindo, L., Van Liew, J. R., & Arch, J. J. (2017). Acceptance and commitment therapy: A transdiagnostic behavioral intervention for mental health and medical conditions. *Neurotherapeutics. The Journal of the American Society for Experimental Neurotherapeutics*, 14(3), 546–553. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13311-017-0521-3>
- Fisher, A. J., Medaglia, J. D., & Jeronimus, B. F. (2018). Lack of group-to-individual generalizability is a threat to human subjects research. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 115(27), E6106–E6115. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1711978115>
- Gertler, P., & Tate, R. L. (2020). Are single item mood scales (SIMS) valid for people with traumatic brain injury? *Brain Injury*, 34(5), 653–664. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02699052.2020.1733087>
- Gloster, A. T., Haller, E., Villanueva, J., & Block, V. (2023). Psychotherapy for chronic in- and outpatients with common mental disorders: The “choose change” effectiveness trial. *Psychotherapy and Psychosomatics*, 92(2), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000529411>
- Gloster, A. T., Klotsche, J., Ciarrochi, J., Eifert, G., Sonntag, R., Wittchen, H.-U., et al. (2017). Increasing valued behaviors precedes reduction in suffering: Findings from a randomized controlled trial using ACT. *Behaviour Research and Therapy*, 91, 64–71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brat.2017.01.013>
- Hayes, S. C., Ciarrochi, J., Hofmann, S. G., Chin, F., & Sahdra, B. (2022). Evolving an idiom approach to processes of change: Towards a unified personalized science of human improvement. *Behaviour Research and Therapy*, 156, 104155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brat.2022.104155>
- Hayes, S. C., Strosahl, K. D., & Wilson, K. G. (2011). *Acceptance and commitment therapy: The process and practice of mindful change* (2nd ed.). Guildford Press.
- Koo, T. K., & Li, M. Y. (2016). A guideline of selecting and reporting intraclass correlation coefficients for reliability research. *Journal of Chiropractic Medicine*, 15(2), 155–163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcm.2016.02.012>
- Molenaar, P. C. (2004). A manifesto on psychology as idiographic science: Bringing the person back into scientific psychology, this time forever. *Measurement*, 2(4), 201–218. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15366359mea0204_1
- Molenaar, P. M. (2013). On the necessity to use person-specific data analysis approaches in psychology. *European Journal of Developmental Psychology*, 10(1), 29–39. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17405629.2012.747435>
- Molenaar, P. C. M., & Campbell, C. G. (2009). The new person-specific paradigm in psychology. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 18(2), 112–117. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8721.2009.01619.x>
- Mouatt, B., Leake, H. B., Stanton, T. R., Moseley, G. L., Simons, L. E., & Braithwaite, F. A. (2023). A single-item mood question adequately discriminates moderately severe to severe depression in individuals with persistent pain: Preliminary validation. *British Journal of Anaesthesia*, 131(4), e137–e139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bja.2023.07.017>
- Munafó, M. R., Nosek, B. A., Bishop, D. V. M., Button, K. S., Chambers, C. D., du Sert, N. P., et al. (2017). A manifesto for reproducible science. *Nature Human Behaviour*, 1(1), 21. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-016-0021>
- Sahdra, B. K., Ciarrochi, J., Fraser, M. I., Yap, K., Haller, E., Hayes, S. C., et al. (2023). The compassion balance: Understanding the interrelation of self- and other-compassion for optimal well-being. *Mindfulness*, 14(8), 1997–2013. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12671-023-02187-4>
- Sahdra, B. K., Ciarrochi, J., Klimczak, K. S., Krafft, J., Hayes, S. C., & Levin, M. (2024). Testing the applicability of idiom statistics in longitudinal studies: The example of ‘doing what matters.’. *Journal of Contextual Behavioral Science*, Article 100728. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcbs.2024.100728>
- Song, J., Howe, E., Oltmanns, J. R., & Fisher, A. J. (2023). Examining the concurrent and predictive validity of single items in ecological momentary assessments. *Assessment*, 30(5), 1662–1671. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10731911221113563>
- Verster, J. C., Sandalova, E., Garssen, J., & Bruce, G. (2021). The use of single-item ratings versus traditional multiple-item questionnaires to assess mood and health. *European Journal of Investigation in Health Psychology and Education*, 11(1), 183–198. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ejihpe11010015>
- Villanueva, J., Meyer, A. H., Rinner, M. T. B., Firsching, V. J., Benoy, C., Brogli, S., et al. (2019). “Choose change”: Design and methods of an acceptance and commitment therapy effectiveness trial for transdiagnostic treatment-resistant patients. *BMC Psychiatry*, 19(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-019-2109-4>